

Relationship of QRS Fragmentation and Coronary Arterial Lesion Severity Assessed with Syntax Scores in Acute Coronary Syndrome Patients in Adam Malik Haji Hospital

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Abstract:-

Background: Almost half of the causes of cardiovascular death are the result of Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI). Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) consisting of unstable angina pectoris (APTS), non-ST elevation acute myocardial infarction (IMANEST) and ST elevation acute myocardial infarction (AMIEST) was the leading cause of death in adults and accounted for 16.7% of deaths from all groups. age. The SYNTAX score is a score system that is comprehensively formulated to describe the complexity of coronary artery lesions based on angiographic results and predict the final outcome of percutaneous coronary intervention (IKAP) or coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). QRS (fQRS) fragmentation on the ECG is associated with the presence of myocardial scarring, ischemia, and fibrosis stemming from defects in signal transduction processes and ventricular depolarization.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between QRS fragmentation and the severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score in patients with acute coronary syndromes.

Methods: The study involved acute coronary syndrome patients who underwent coronary angiography at the Haji Adam Malik General Hospital in Medan in the period January 2020 to October 2020. All subjects underwent ECG examination and SYNTAX score assessment. Statistical analysis was performed to assess QRS fragmentation with the severity of coronary artery lesions.

Results: 27 subjects with QRS fragmentation experienced moderate-severe lesion severity as many as 25 people (46.3%) and only 2 people with low lesion severity (3.7%), while 22 subjects without QRS fragmentation had lesion severity. low coronary arteries and only 5 people (9.3%) had moderate-severe lesions. Based on the analysis, there was a statistically significant relationship between QRS fragmentation images and the severity of coronary artery lesions in patients with acute coronary syndromes with p value < 0.001 . Patients with QRS fragmentation compared with non-fragmented QRS patients had a 35x risk of experiencing moderate-severe severity. A total of 27 subjects found that QRS fragmentation had a

moderate strength relationship with the SYNTAX score and the direction of the correlation was positive and statistically significant.

Conclusion: There is a relationship between QRS fragmentation in patients with acute coronary syndromes and the severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score.

Keywords:- acute coronary syndrome, SYNTAX score, QRS fragment fragmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Coronary heart disease (CHD) is a disease caused by plaque that builds up in the coronary arteries that supply oxygen to the heart muscle. This disease is one of the most common cardiovascular diseases. Reports from the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2013 as many as 17.5 million people die each year due to cardiovascular disease, about 31% of the total deaths worldwide. The highest cause of death after stroke is coronary heart disease, which is 12.9% of the total population, according to survey data in 2014. ¹ Almost half of the causes of cardiovascular death are due to Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI). ²

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) consisting of unstable angina pectoris (APTS), non-ST elevation acute myocardial infarction (IMANEST) and ST elevation acute myocardial infarction (AMIEST) was the leading cause of death in adults and accounted for 16.7% of deaths from all groups. age. ³

A large number of scoring systems and laboratory parameters have been used in clinical practice to assess the severity and complexity of coronary artery lesions. One of them that is often used is the SYNTAX score. ⁴ Score SYNTAX score system is formulated comprehensively to describe the complexity of coronary artery lesions based on the results of angiography and predict the final outcome of percutaneous coronary interventions (IKAP) or coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). ^{5,6}

QRS (fQRS) fragmentation on the ECG is associated with the presence of myocardial scarring, ischemia, and fibrosis stemming from defects in signal transduction processes and ventricular depolarization. ^{7,8} Fragmentation originates from abnormally small areas of the myocardium

where ventricular activation is delayed and is asynchronous. Partial damage to the conduction system in the ventricles causes notching of the QRS segment on the ECG. ⁹

Tarek et al (2013) in their study reported that the presence of fQRS on the ECG recording at the time of the ACS event indicated the presence of myocardial scarring or fibrosis and described the severity of coronary lesions. ¹⁰ Furthermore, a study by Bekler et al (2015) reported that QRS fragmentation on a 12-lead ECG at admission was associated with the severity and complexity of coronary artery lesions in patients with acute coronary syndromes. ⁴

In this study, the authors tried to see if there was a correlation between QRS complex fragmentation and the severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score in acute coronary syndrome patients at H.Adam Malik Hospital Medan.

II. METHOD

A. Research population

The data of this study were taken from acute coronary syndrome patients who underwent coronary angiography at Haji Adam Malik General Hospital Medan in the period January 2020 to October 2020 with the *consecutive sampling method*. The study involved 54 patients with acute coronary syndrome at Haji Adam Malik General Hospital, who were willing to be contacted and interviewed by telephone or face to face. Patients with atrial fibrillation rhythms and with QRS complex duration 120 ms were excluded from the study.

B. ECG Evaluation and SYNTAX Score

This research is a descriptive analytic study with a cross-sectional design. An ECG was performed to assess QRS fragmentation. Furthermore, the severity of coronary artery lesions was assessed and the SYNTAX score was calculated, where a score of 22 was a low SYNTAX score and a score >22 was a moderate-severe SYNTAX score.

C. Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software. To assess the hypothesis test to assess whether there is a relationship between QRS fragmentation from the ECG and the SYNTAX score obtained from coronary angiography in patients with acute myocardial infarction using the Chi-square test if the condition χ^2 is met, but if these conditions are not met then the alternative *Fisher exact test* is used. For numerical variables, statistical tests using *T independent test* on data that are normally distributed, and Mann-Whitney test on data that are not normally distributed. Then a multivariate analysis will be carried out using logistic regression. The p value < 0.05 was said to be statistically significant.

D. Research results

Patients with acute coronary syndrome who underwent coronary angiography at the Haji Adam Malik Hospital in Medan in the period January 2020 to October 2020 found 54 patients with QRS fragmentation and without QRS fragmentation who had met the inclusion and exclusion criteria, consisting of 44 patients (81.5%) male . -male and 10

patients (18.5%) female with a mean age of 52 years for patients with QRS fragmentation and 55 years for patients without QRS fragmentation. The distribution of the characteristics of the research subjects is presented in table 1.

Characteristics	Total (n = 54)
Age	53.83±9.125
Gender, n(%)	
Man	44 (81.5%)
Woman	10 (18.5%)
Hypertension, Yes	29 (53%)
Diabetes, Yes	25 (46%)
Smoking, Yes	44 (81%)
Vital Sign	
HR	75.5 (54-115)
TDS	133±19.4
TDD	70 (60-110)
Laboratory	
Hemoglobin	14.5 (11.7-16.2)
Leukocytes	11,420 (5,740-23,990)
Platelets	246,000 (155,200-407,000)
urea	24 (13-73)
Creatinine	1.02 (0.5-2.8)
Sodium	136.46±3.28
Potassium	3.94±0.50
Chloride	104 (92-121)
Admission blood sugar	178 (69-555)
Fasting blood sugar	119 (75-257)
Blood sugar 2 hours post prandial	139 (82-272)
HbA1C	6.35 (5.20-14.0)
Total Cholesterol	176.95±29.63
Triglycerides	147.5 (76-416)
HDL	34.5(19-66)
LDL	123 (49-182)
CKMB	80 (21-925)
Troponin I	2.35 (0.05-27)
SKA, n(%)	
IMA-EST	35 (64.8%)
IMA-NST	19 (35.2%)
Lesions, n(%)	
1VD	23 (42.6%)
MVD	31 (57.4%)
EF (%)	47.5±9.6
SYNTAX Score	22.45±9.14

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Subjects

From 54 research subjects, 30 people (55.5%) with a SYNTAX score > 22 had a mean age of 53.43±9.21 years and 24 people (44.4%) with a SYNTAX score (≤22) had a mean age of 54, 33±9.18. There were no statistically significant differences in age, gender, risk factors, vital sign examination, laboratory values and echocardiography between the two groups. From coronary angiography examination, it was found that there was a significant difference in the number of coronary artery lesions and SYNTAX scores, with the number of patients with syntax scores > 22 in the 1VD group were 8 people (29.62%) and in

the MVD group were 22 people (81, 48 %) with p value = 0.008. The characteristics of the research subjects based on

the SYNTAX score are presented in table 2.

Characteristics	SYNTAX Score		p Nilai value
	Moderate-severe (>22) n=30	Low (22) n=24	
Age	53.43±9.21	54.33±9.18	0.722
Gender, n(%)			
Man	25 (56.8)	19 (43.2)	0.736
Woman	5 (50.0)	5 (500)	
Hypertension, Yes	16 (55.2)	13 (44.8)	0.951
Diabetes, Yes	15 (60.0)	10 (40.0)	0.542
Smoking, Yes	23 (52,3)	21 (47.7)	0.309
Vital Sign			
HR	74 (60-115)	80 (54-98)	0.638
TDS	131±20.4	135±18,13	0.282
TDD	70 (65-110)	70 (60-100)	0.556
Laboratory			
Hemoglobin	14.17±1.23	14.63±0.98	0.145
Leukocytes	10,795 (5,900-23,990)	12,845 (5,740-17,020)	0.459
Platelets	243,000 (155,200-407,000)	254,500 (197.00-354,000)	0.607
urea	24 (13-66)	24 (17-73)	0.793
Creatinine	1.07 (0.60-2.80)	0.90 (0.50-1.56)	0.261
Sodium	136.03±3.87	137.00±2.32	0.262
Potassium	3.90±0.50	4.00±0.50	0.505
Chloride	102 (92-121)	105 (92-121)	0.552
KGDS admission	161 (79-296)	186.5(69-555)	0.497
KGDN	140.50 (75-257)	115 (82-257)	0.233
KG2PP	137.5 (82 -272)	156.33 (100-240)	0.986
HbA1C	6.2 (5.20-12.80)	6.5 (5.4-14.0)	0.701
Total Cholesterol	171.13±32.06	184.22±24.97	0.107
Triglycerides	133 (80-416)	186 (76-288)	0.192
HDL	34.5 (19-52)	34.5 (26-66)	0.787
LDL	119.10±31.39	133.66±25.27	0.071
CKMB	77.5 (30.0-925.0)	85.5 (0.21-450.0)	0.389
Troponin I	5 (0.05-27.00)	1.2 (0.05-8.0)	<0.001
SKA, n(%)			
STEMI	18 (51.4)	17 (48.6)	0.407
NSTEMI	12 (63.2)	7 (36.8)	
Lesions, n(%)			
1VD	8 (34.8)	15 (65.2)	0.028
MVD	22 (71.0)	9 (29.0)	0.008
EF (%)	45.96±9.90	49.41±9.05	0.192

Table 2: Characteristics of research subjects based on the SYNTAX . score

Research subjects with QRS fragmentation as many as 27 people experienced moderate-severe lesion severity as many as 25 people (46.3%) and those with low lesion severity only 2 people (3.7%), while study subjects without QRS fragmentation as many as 27 people experienced severity moderate-severe lesions as many as 5 people (9.3%)

and low severity as many as 22 people (40.7%). Based on the analysis, there was a statistically significant relationship between the QRS fragmentation image and the severity of coronary artery lesions in patients with acute coronary syndromes with p<0.001.

	Severity of coronary artery lesion n(%)		Total	p Nilai value
	SYNTAX score moderate-severe (>22)	Low SYNTAX score (≤22)		
QRS Fragmentation (+)	25 (46.3)	2 (3,7)	27 (50.0)	<0.001
QRS Fragmentation (-)	5 (9.3)	22 (40.7)	27 (50.0)	
Total	30 (55.6)	29 (44.4)	54 (100.0)	

Table 3: Relationship between QRS fragmentation features and severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score in patients with acute coronary syndromes

Chi Square Test

Patients with fQRS (+) compared with patients with fQRS (-) had a 35x risk of experiencing moderate-severe severity which was statistically significant with [β 3,573; OR 35,622 (95% CI 5,89-215,16) p<0.001]. Elevated troponin levels had a 1.3x risk of coronary artery lesion severity but not statistically significant with [β 0.302; OR 1,352 (CI 95% 0.973-1.879) p value = 0.072].

	Variable	Beta Coefficient	p Nilai value	OR	95% CI		
					Min	max	
Step 1 ^a	fQRS(+)	4.372	.010	79,205	2.816	2228,046	
	Hemoglobin	-.101	.861	.904	.294	2,781	
	KGDN	.005	.635	1.005	.985	1.025	
	TotChol	.004	.933	1.004	.919	1.096	
	TGA	-.011	.433	.989	.961	1.017	
	LDL	-.013	.739	.987	.915	1.065	
	EF	.048	.547	1.049	.898	1.225	
	MVD	.101	.939	1.106	.083	14,673	
	Troponin_I	.338	.141	1,402	.894	2,199	
	Constant	-1.318	.901	.268			
Step 2 ^a	fQRS(+)	4.433	.004	84,185	4.281	1655,377	
	Hemoglobin	-.087	.873	.917	.316	2,658	
	KGDN	.005	.591	1.005	.987	1.024	
	TotChol	.004	.934	1.004	.919	1.096	
	TGA	-.012	.408	.989	.962	1.016	
	LDL	-.013	.741	.987	.915	1.065	
	EF	.046	.546	1.047	.901	1.218	
	Troponin_I	.335	.136	1.398	.900	2.172	
	Constant	-1.407	.894	.245			
	Step 3 ^a	fQRS(+)	4.392	.002	80,771	5.086	1282,682
Hemoglobin		-.107	.826	.899	.346	2,336	
KGDN		.005	.577	1.005	.987	1.024	
TGA		-.011	.154	.989	.975	1.004	
LDL		-.010	.612	.990	.953	1.029	
EF		.043	.503	1.044	.921	1.184	
Troponin_I		.329	.118	1.389	.920	2,098	
Constant		-.789	.916	.454			
Step 4 ^a		fQRS(+)	4.410	.002	82,243	5.107	1324,365
		KGDN	.005	.561	1.005	.987	1.024
	TGA	-.011	.124	.989	.975	1.003	
	LDL	-.012	.527	.988	.953	1.025	
	EF	.045	.478	1.046	.923	1.186	
	Troponin_I	.330	.114	1.391	.924	2,093	
	Constant	-2,179	.587	.113			
Step 5 ^a	fQRS(+)	4,546	.001	94,210	5.761	1540,521	
	TGA	-.011	.116	.989	.975	1.003	
	LDL	-.010	.576	.990	.955	1.026	
	EF	.049	.442	1.050	.927	1.191	
	Troponin_I	.342	.093	1,408	.945	2,099	
	Constant	-1.861	.632	156			

Step 6 ^a	fQRS(+)	4.783	.001	119,428	7.135	1999.042
	TGA	-.012	.110	.988	.974	1.003
	EF	.053	.424	1.054	.926	1,199
	Troponin_I	.326	.099	1.386	.940	2,042
	Constant	-3.212	.302	.040		
Step 7 ^a	fQRS(+)	4.343	.000	76,964	6,731	880.072
	TGA	-.009	.147	.991	.980	1.003
	Troponin_I	.278	.128	1,320	.923	1.888
	Constant	-.954	.417	.385		
Step 8 ^a	fQRS(+)	3.573	.000	35,622	5.898	215,162
	Troponin_I	.302	.072	1,352	.973	1,879
	Constant	-2.298	.002	.100		

Table 4: Factors that act as markers of the severity of coronary lesions in patients with acute coronary syndrome

The results of this study indicate that the sensitivity value is 83.3%, the specificity is 91.7%, the positive predictive value (NPP) is 92.6% and the negative predictive value (NPN) is 81.5% (table 5).

Parameter	p	n	minimum IK	Maximum IK
Sensitivity	0.833	30	0.700	0.966
Specificity	0.917	24	0.807	1.027
NPP	0.926	27	0.827	1.025
NPN	0.815	27	0.669	0.961

Table 5: Value of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (NPP), and negative predictive value (NPN) of QRS fragmentation with SYNTAX score

The relationship between the number of QRS fragmentation locations and the Syntax score in patients with acute coronary syndrome is presented in table 6 and the *scatter plot graph* in Figure 1. A total of 27 subjects found QRS fragmentation had a moderate strength relationship with the SYNTAX score and the direction of the correlation was positive and statistically significant. [r=0.648; p<0.001].

	SYNTAX Score
Number of QRS locations	n = 27 r = 0.648 p<0.001

Table 6: The relationship between the number of fQRS locations and the Syntax score in patients with acute coronary syndrome

Fig. 1: Scatter plot of the relationship between the number of fQRS sites and the SYNTAX score in acute coronary syndrome patients

III. DISCUSSION

In this study, it was found that QRS fragmentation in patients with acute coronary syndromes was associated with the severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score. Research subjects with QRS fragmentation as many as 27 people experienced moderate-severe lesion severity as many as 25 people (46.3%) and only 2 people experiencing low lesion severity (3.7%), while 22 subjects without QRS fragmentation had coronary artery lesion severity. low and only 5 people (9.3%) had moderate-severe lesions.

Rahman et al. in Egypt found a correlation of QRS fragmentation and severity of coronary obstruction in IMA-NEST patients. Fragmented QRS is more common in the elderly, men, smokers, diabetes and dyslipidemia. A higher frequency of QRS fragmentation was also found in patients with multivessel disease, high troponin levels and high syntax scores.¹¹

Research by Bekler et al. demonstrated that the number of fQRS leads on a 12-lead ECG at admission was associated with severity in patients with ACS. As objective methods, the SYNTAX and Gensini scores can evaluate the severity of CHD, and it has been demonstrated that they are associated with both short-term and long-term cardiovascular risk and revascularization.¹² These two scoring systems reflect coronary anatomy, arterial morphology, and severity of stenosis in atherosclerotic lesions.¹³

QRS fragmentation is associated with increased morbidity and mortality and is also a predictor of adverse cardiac events in patients with ACS¹⁴ idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy (CMP)¹⁵, and decompensated heart failure.¹⁶ QRS fragmentation results from fibrosis/scar and regional myocardial ischemia, leading to heterogeneous electrical activation of the myocardium.¹⁷ Fragmented QRS has been shown to be associated with myocardial fibrosis in patients with ischemic or non-ischemic left ventricular dysfunction.

Pietrasik and Zareba demonstrated the sensitivity of QRS fragmentation in detecting myocardial lesions, and confirmed that the presence of QRS fragmentation can be used to predict cardiac events.⁸ In a previous study, Peters et al. demonstrated that QRS fragmentation is a diagnostic sign of arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia or CMP, which is associated with right ventricular scarring.¹⁸ These results indicate that the QRS fragmentation complex is a non-invasive ECG parameter that is easily evaluated and is associated with cardiac fibrosis. These data also explain why the number of QRS fragmentation leads was significantly higher in ACS patients with high SYNTAX scores in our study.

QRS fragmentation is a simple, widely available and inexpensive marker for ACS patients. In an era of universal health coverage with limited financial support, cost-effective diagnostic tools and prognostic markers will be urgently needed. Further research on QRS fragmentation will make it more recognized and used especially if it has been

established as a pathognomonic ECG finding. Further studies will be needed to confirm the use of QRS fragmentation in patients with ACS.¹⁹

IV. CONCLUSION

There is a relationship between QRS fragmentation in patients with acute coronary syndrome and the severity of coronary artery lesions as assessed by the SYNTAX score at Haji Adam Malik General Hospital.

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